

QUALITY OF WORK-LIFE: ITS MODERATING ROLE ON FILIPINO GEN Z'S OCCUPATIONAL SELF-EFFICACY AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT

*Maria Zarah Elaine M. Alilio^{1,2}, Lyza Andrea F. Bautista^{1,3},
Veronica E. Capariño^{1,4}, Jemima M. Tubu^{1,5}, and Jason O. Manaois^{1,6}*

¹ *Polytechnic University of the Philippines, Sta. Mesa, Manila, Philippines*

² *Philippine Women's University, Malate, Manila, Philippines*

³ *University of Rizal System - College of Science, Tanay, Rizal, Philippines*

⁴ *PSO Manila Limited, Bonifacio Global City, Taguig, Philippines*

⁵ *National Development Company, Makati City, Philippines*

⁶ *Mindanao State University – Iligan Institute of Technology, Iligan City, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This research examined the interplay between quality of work-life (QWL), occupational self-efficacy, and organizational commitment among Filipino Gen Z employees. Employing a quantitative research design with moderation path analysis, the research explored the strength and direction of associations. Descriptive statistics summarize the data for each variable. The sample consists of 101 Filipino Gen Z workers (born between 1997 and 2012) who completed a 20-minute online questionnaire encompassing QWL, occupational self-efficacy, and organizational commitment. The findings showed that a healthier QWL positively correlates with increased commitment to the organization. In conclusion, the study showed that when Gen Z is satisfied with their work-life balance, it translates more effectively into dedication and commitment to their job.

Keywords: occupational self-efficacy, organizational commitment, quality of work-life, moderation analysis, Gen Z

INTRODUCTION

Generation Z (Gen Z) were those born from 1997 to 2012, and have garnered significant attention not only in social contexts but also within the labor force. A study identified factors shaping Gen Z, namely social connections, education and learning, information consumption, globalism, technological dependence, world affinity culture, and life expectancy (Tidhar, 2023).

The labor force is now experiencing a noticeable shift as this new generation becomes actively involved. This young generation showed that they possess a unique set of qualities and characteristics that set them apart from generations in the workforce. They are highly adept at using technology and crave constant stimulation and feedback. However, there is some research showing that they value work-life balance and a purposeful career. Thus, this research delves into the concept of Quality of Work-Life (QWL), which pertains to an individual's satisfaction and well-being concerning the balance between work demands and personal life.

Studies on Generation Z's level of organizational commitment revealed that unlike earlier generations who, most of the time, resort to settling with one company, Generation Z is most likely to be a "job-hopping" generation, meaning that they do not stay on one company (Nabahani, et.,al, 2020). For particular reasons, they tend to always seek another job every time they have the opportunity. Therefore, being the generation that is currently joining the workforce, it is essential to promote a healthy working environment and greater opportunity for advancement.

Quality Work-life and Organizational Commitment

Quality of work life is universal (Ishak et al. 2018). Certainly, it's essential for organizations, whether small or large companies, to prioritize a conducive work environment and enhance employee's commitment to work. In the study of Johari et al. (2018), it accentuates the importance of having established balance between work and personal life as it drives the employees to be more productive, be motivated, and especially decreases the chance to acquire stress in the working station.

A local study conducted in the Elementary School of Alegria District, Cebu City in the Elementary and Secondary level wherein 134 females and 20 males teachers had participated to determine if demographic profile such as age, gender, highest educational attainment, marital status, number of household members in the family and number of years in service has a relationship with quality work-life. The findings based on the statistical result showed that only the number of household members in the family has significantly affected QWL while other factors have no significant association. Additionally, they have also examined if demographic profile and organizational commitment has a relationship. The outcome has shown no significant association. This means that the teachers' perceived organizational commitment can be strengthened by means of how intrinsically motivated they are. Kaplan and Kaplan (2018) added that

employees' values towards the organization is a significant idea considering the fact that it affects the commitment of an individual's, organizations, and society at large.

Furthermore, one foreign study from Kerman province hospital of Iran, conducted research for 51 emergency nurses between 30 and 40 years old. The result showed that organizational commitment and quality of work life has a positive and significant relationship. Studies support their data which indicates a positive significant relationship between quality of work life for continuous commitment and normative commitment. However, it appears that quality of work life and personal and professional information (age, educational level, service record) is inconsequential.

Collectively, these studies provide valuable insights into Generation Z's behavior and other factors affecting their work. Consequently, these findings and data will serve as the guiding framework of this research, which aims to explore the correlation of organizational commitment, occupational self-efficacy and quality of work-life.

Theoretical Framework

By assessing the current state of Generation Z workers, the study aims to provide valuable insights to organizations undergoing continuous hiring and organizational redefinition. Researchers selected QWL, organizational commitment and occupational self-efficacy as key variables to explore the connections of theories related from one another.

The Three (3) Components Model of Commitment by John Meyer and Natalie Allen's which includes: affective commitment (emotional attachment), continuance commitment (costs associated with leaving) and normative commitment (sense of obligation) has an alignment with Albert Bandura's concept of self-efficacy, which is the belief in one's ability to successfully perform, a specific task or behavior.

For instance, Herzberg's Two Factor Theory/ Motivation-Hygiene Theory revealed that certain characteristics of a job are consistently related to job satisfaction whilst different factors are interrelated to job satisfaction (Dartey-Baah, 2011). It highlights the importance of providing motivating factors for employees which can ultimately improve their quality of work life and lead to higher commitment and motivation.

Figure 1. Moderation Model of Quality of Work-Life, Occupational Self-Efficacy, Organizational Commitment

Research Questions

The purpose of the study is to delve and investigate the moderating role of quality of work-life between occupational self-efficacy and organizational commitment among Filipino Gen Z employees, and to address and identify the direct relationship between the variables, the researchers formulated the following research questions:

1. Is there a relationship between occupational self-efficacy, organizational commitment and quality of work-life among employed Filipino Gen Z?
2. Does quality of work-life have a moderating effect on Filipino Gen Z's self-efficacy and organizational commitment?
3. To what extent does the quality of work-life affect the organizational commitment of Filipino Gen Z employees?

METHODOLOGY

The Participants

The participants of the research study are Filipino Gen Z, who were born between 1997 - 2012 and range in age from 22 - 27 years old, there were varied numbers of participants for each age group in which represents a unique population to study the relationship of quality of work-life to self-efficacy and organizational commitment, wherein, researchers can gain valuable insights evolving workplace dynamics in the Philippines. The research study consists of a total of 35 men and 66 women, ages 22 to 27 years of age, who worked as Gen Z employees and to guarantee the statistical results were reliable, the researchers collected a total of 101 respondents from the educational institution/s, government agencies, business process outsourcing (BPO) companies, telecommunications, military, construction, logistics and finance industries who worked

in various organizations with a wide range of professional backgrounds.

Measures

Occupational self-efficacy Scale. The OCCSEFF scale was developed by Dr. Birgit Schysand Dr. Gernot Von Collani (2002). The scale consists of twenty (20) items with seven identified items being reversed scores (e.g. *When I set goals for myself in my job I rarely achieve them.*) OCCSEFF assesses the perceived general self-efficacy of an individual in the occupational context. A Likert-type response scale with categories ranging from 1 as “completely true” to 6 as “not at all true”. A perceived assessment of the respondent's occupational self-efficacy is obtained through averaging the responses across all items. A higher average score indicates a higher perceived occupational self-efficacy. Furthermore, the Cronbach's had a.92 alpha.

Three-Component Model Employee Commitment Survey. TCM Employee Commitment Survey by Meyer, Allen, & Smith (2004). The revised survey has a total of eighteen (18) items which measures three (3) forms of employee commitment to an organization, namely, affective commitment (desire-based), normative commitment (obligation-based) and continuance commitment (cost-based). Each factor consists of six (6) items, with four identified items being reversed-keyed (e.g. *I am not afraid of what might happen if I quit my job without having another one lined up.*). The survey used a 7-likert scale, indicating the level of agreement from 1 as “strongly disagree”, 2 as “disagree”, 3 as “slightly disagree”, 4 as “undecided”, 5 as “slightly agree”, 6 as “agree”, and 7 as “strongly agree”. The responses are averaged to determine the final score, with a higher score indicating a better level of organizational commitment. TCM Employee Commitment Survey indicate good psychometric features, the following were the Cronbach Alpha factor scores: ACS (affective commitment) = 0.87; NCS (normative commitment) = 0.79; CCS (continuance commitment) = 0.75.

Work-Related Quality of Life Scale-2. WRQoLS-2 is the second version of Work-related Quality of Life Scale (WRQoLS) authored by Simon Easton & Darren Van Laar (2007), the second version contains thirty-two (32) items (with overall Cronbach's Alpha of 0.94), it offers improved psychometric qualities from the original scale. The 32-item version of the WRQoL-2 contains all of the original WRQoL 1 scale questions. The scale assessing the overall quality of worklife of an employee. The scale is clustered into seven factors - control at work, employee engagement, and general well-being, home-work interface, job career satisfaction, stress at work, and working conditions. Using a 5-point Likert scale with the response category indicating level of agreement ranging from 1 as “strongly disagree”, 2 as “neutral” 3 as “agree”, 4 as “strongly agree” and 5 as “strongly agree”, scores on five items must be reversed. (e.g. *I often feel under pressure at work.*). The overall score is achieved by taking the average of the factor scores, providing a comprehensive overview of individuals' quality of work-life. Higher scores reflect greater quality of work-life. While the WRQoLS-2 is currently being tested, the reported internal consistency of the Chinese translation of the scale (WRQoLS-2C) is Cronbach's alpha = 0.94.

Data Gathering Procedures

A survey was distributed to selected Filipino Gen Z employees across the country, using a purposive sampling method. Following the participants' identification, the researchers disseminated an informed consent, followed through by the online survey questionnaire which were both via Google forms. The survey comprised questions about organizational commitment, occupational self-efficacy, and quality of work-life (QWL). Google Spreadsheet was used to generate the data that was gathered from the research participants, and only the researchers had access to it.

Data Analysis

The research study is quantitative in nature with correlational approach and moderated regression analysis that allows to measure the variables and assess the strength and direction of the associations and a descriptive statistic to summarize data for each variable.

Scope and Limitations

The researchers acknowledged the importance of offering substantial insights into the professional situations of a growing population of employed Filipino Gen Zs in the Philippines. Hence, this research study primarily focuses on three assumptions - influence of the Filipino Gen Z workers, their compelling motive to be crucial for organizations, and the Philippine setting as a factor for quality work-life. However, due to the limited sample size of the research study, it is impossible to determine with certainty whether it is applicable to the entirety of the Filipino Gen Z employees in the Philippines.

RESULTS

The researchers showed the obtained findings from the data analysis, outlining the relationship between quality of work-life, self-efficacy and organizational commitment among Filipino Gen Z.

The presented descriptive statistics in table 1 demonstrated the participants perceived occupational self-efficacy, organizational commitment, and quality of work-life. The participants showed a moderate to low perceived occupational self-efficacy with a mean score of 2.43. On organizational commitment, respondents demonstrated a mean score of 4.83 suggesting an average level of commitment to their current organization. In a similar case, participants' quality of work life revealed a moderate to high satisfaction on work-related factors of their life with the mean score of 3.53.

Table 1: Descriptives and Correlation Matrix

	n	Mean	SD	OSE	OC	QWL
Occupational Self-efficacy	101	2.43	0.569	-	-	-
Organizational Commitment	101	4.83	0.668	-0.218	-	-
Quality of Work-life	101	3.53	0.511	-0.427	0.423	-

Research Problem 1: *Is there a relationship between occupational self-efficacy, organizational commitment and quality of work-life among employed Filipino Gen Z?*

Table 1 shows several results, first, the computed Pearson's r between occupational self-efficacy and organizational commitment is -0.218, indicating no relevant relationship. . Secondly, the results show that there is no positive correlation between occupational self-efficacy and quality of work-life with -0.427 computed Person's r. Lastly, table 1 revealed that there is a positive relationship between quality of work-life and organizational commitment. This implies that as quality of work-life, organizational commitment also increases.

Research Problem 2: *Does quality of work-life have a moderating effect on Filipino Gen Z's self-efficacy and organizational commitment?*

Results presented in table 2 shows that there is no direct interaction effect on the combined occupational self-efficacy and quality of work-life to the organizational commitment of working Generation Z. This suggests that the quality of work-life does not have a moderation effect on the interaction between occupational self-efficacy and organizational commitment.

Table 2: Moderation Estimates

	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		Z	p
			Lower	Upper		
OSE (IV)	-0.0525	0.111	-0.257	0.173	-0.474	0.635
QWL (MV)	0.5642	0.163	0.237	0.875	3.468	< .001
OSE (IV) * QWL (MV)	0.2254	0.202	-0.181	0.615	1.115	0.265

Research Problem 3: *To what extent does the quality of work-life affect the organizational commitment of Filipino Gen Z employees?*

Although the data presented in table 2 revealed that there is no relationship between occupation self-efficacy and organization commitment, and suggest that there is no direct interaction effect on the combined occupational self-efficacy and quality of work-life to the organizational commitment. The results in table 2 displayed that quality of work-life shows direct effect to organizational commitment with a p-value of $<.001$ and an estimate of 0.56 implying the higher the quality of work-life the higher the organizational commitment of Filipino Gen Z.

DISCUSSION

The research study found no significant relationship between self-efficacy and organizational commitment among Filipino Gen Z - the result could be explained with the high levels of self-efficacy among Filipino Gen Z workers which may not translate into strong organizational commitment if work demands long hours that interferes with personal life. However, the quality of work-life leads to organizational commitment, with higher quality implying greater commitment. The interaction effect of occupational self-efficacy and quality of work-life had no moderating effect on organizational commitment - there is a chance that other factors could may have explained the association between the quality of work-life, self-efficacy and organizational commitment and that the sample size used in the research is insufficient to thoroughly explain and explore this relationship. The result is contrary to previous study conducted by Orgambidez, Borrego and Vasquez-Aguado (2020) which found self-efficacy a significant predictor of quality of work-life, but partially mediated by job satisfaction and work engagement. The disparity between the previous and present research study highlights the importance for a thorough investigation of the variables affecting organizational commitment suggesting potential other factors at play and some factors in the past may not be as crucial today, and vice versa.

In accordance with the study, Gen Z's confidence in their professional abilities has no direct impact on the decision for continued employment with a company. However, a positive quality of work-life as well as the work environment are significant predictors of organizational commitment. Quality of work-life improves commitment, regardless of self-efficacy. This suggests that to retain Filipino Gen Z employees, organizations should emphasize on creating a positive work environment that prioritizes well-being and foster growth opportunities and although Filipino Gen Z has confidence with their skills and knowledge, they put greater value for a holistic experience for their professional and personal welfare. With this, the limitations of the research make it indefinitely applicable to all Gen Z, but highlights the importance of quality of work-life in this generation.

Conclusions

The research study among Filipino Generation Z (Gen Z) employees showed that having an excellent quality of work-life is a more important source of retention than self-

confidence in their professional skills. Interestingly, their desire for a healthy quality of work-life appears to be unaffected by their total self-efficacy. The result emphasizes the significance of focusing on the quality of work-life programs for Gen Z employees. Even if they have high levels of self-confidence in their abilities, a poor balance between work and life, can outweigh their sense of fulfillment and be immediate to seek employment elsewhere. This suggests that Gen Z employees prioritize workplaces that emphasize and respect their time outside of work and offer a sustainable workplace. In addition, it appears that Filipino culture conveys an essential factor when it comes to personal, work and family space of an individual.

Recommendations

The research conducted found a positive relationship between occupational self-efficacy, quality of work-life and organizational commitment among Gen Z employees, while there is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and organizational commitment, quality of work-life and organizational commitment, quality of work-life are significantly correlated. Researchers suggest conducting a longitudinal research study to examine Gen Z's occupational self-efficacy, quality of work-life and organizational commitment over time and compare the results to previous generations; employ and improve self-efficacy tools and/or assessment to use in a study and explore potential moderating factors which may influence the association between self-efficacy and organizational commitment such as type of industry, company culture and individual personality traits of Filipino Gen Z workers; and finally, consider a larger sample size that could strengthen the generalizability of the research finding/s. The resulting knowledge may assist organizations to develop and implement methods for cultivating a more engaged and dedicated labor force, as well as reduce turnover risk, and also suggests that organizations have to concentrate in creating an ideal work environment for employees and generations to come.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers observed the ethical welfare of the participants which allowed them the right to withdraw anytime, discussed the boundaries of the study and the results of their questionnaires if they wished to have it. The participants acknowledged the informed consent as proof of their willingness to participate and that they are not forced in any way. The full confidentiality of the participants will be treated with full responsibility as only the researchers had access to it.

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